

Categoría	Subcategoría	Identificación	Fuente
Instrumentos para evaluación	Evaluación de recursos académicos (checklist)	CARS (Credibility, Accuracy, Reasonableness, Support)	https://bit.ly/3aRzKmN
		RADAR (Relevance, Authority, Date, Appearance, Reason for writing)	https://bit.ly/3vy9HJb
		CRAAP (Currency, Relevance, Authority, Accuracy, Purpose)	https://bit.ly/3nMC3wR
	Evaluación de fuentes de noticias	SMART (checklist)	https://bit.ly/3u84OpL
		jSMELL (checklist)	https://bit.ly/3aTc2Xk
		«Is this story share-worthy?» (infografía)	https://bit.ly/2PtkvJo
		«IM VA/IN» journalism acronym	https://bit.ly/3umV1MI
		International Fact-Checking Network	https://bit.ly/3xEKyOM
	Detección de «fake news»	«How To Spot Fake News» (checklist)	https://bit.ly/2QLna1p
		Zimdars' tips	https://bit.ly/3nl0Ld
		«How to Fact Check Like a Pro»	https://bit.ly/3aQt880
		The Breaking News Consumer's Handbook (BNCH)	https://bit.ly/3gT2izV
	Tests / Cuestionarios	Snopes	https://bit.ly/3u7Zq6n
«Information Literacy (IL) Test» Manual		https://bit.ly/2OkXfMW	

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		News Media Literacy	https://bit.ly/3gRkLNr
		ACRL Framework for Information Literacy for Higher Education	https://bit.ly/3xC2zgC
		AASL Standards Framework for Learners	https://bit.ly/3vAKo9d
		Core Principles of Media Literacy (National Association for Media Literacy Education - NAMLE)	https://bit.ly/3aSwY0s
Diseño pedagógico	Marcos competenciales (frameworks)	Integración de las competencias ALFIN/AMI en el sistema educativo: referencias, contexto y propuestas	https://bit.ly/335ttPW
		COR (Civic Online Reasoning) Curriculum	https://cor.stanford.edu/
		Common Sense Media's K-12 Digital Citizenship Curriculum	https://bit.ly/3dmUFQi
		The College, Career, and Civic Life (C3) Framework for Social Studies State Standards.	https://bit.ly/3u9PbhF
	Métodos	The SIFT Method (Four Moves)	https://bit.ly/3nAW6hu
		Thou Shalt Not Commit Logical Fallacies	https://bit.ly/2QNTHE5
		DOUBT	https://bit.ly/3eOqG30

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Recursos educativos	Repositorios y plataformas educativas	ACRL Framework for Information Literacy Sandbox	https://bit.ly/3vut8CE
		CORA Community of Online Research Assignments	https://bit.ly/3u7Vu5B
		Newsela	https://bit.ly/3u7zZlh
		Checkology virtual classroom	https://bit.ly/3u2K037
		First Draft News	https://bit.ly/3gOeJ09
	Videojuegos	Factitious	https://bit.ly/3uacgAY
		Bad News	https://bit.ly/3nExXq8
		Fake it To Make it	https://bit.ly/3gWNCjo
		iReporter	https://bbc.in/2QLyyKP